

Onderzoek bestrijdingsmiddelen en omwonenden
(OBO-2) *Residential Exposure to Pesticides and Health Effects*

**WP2: Exposure Assessment: Environmental and
human exposure from sideways and upward spraying**

D2.1 - Study protocol

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1 General information

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2 Summary

Introduction and motivation

The application of pesticides (in particular agricultural/professional? chemical plant protection products) near residential areas has sparked widespread concern and discussions about potential health risks for individuals living in proximity to agricultural land and growers (or pesticides users) themselves. In phase one of the OBO project, researchers addressed residential environmental exposure from boom spraying applications. However, the exposure model developed within OBO was solely verified for downward spraying in flower bulbs. Currently, there is a lack of verified models for exposure assessment regarding sideways and upwards directed spraying. These spraying techniques are used in bush and tree crops (e.g. vines, berries, top fruits, tree nursery) and fruit crops. These crops cover a relevant surface of the Netherlands. Hence, verification of the sideways and upwards modelling would allow to include spraying techniques used in the Netherlands into the exposure assessment. This would reduce exposure misclassification for homes close to agricultural fields where these techniques are commonly used (e.g. fruit crops and tree cultivation).

Aim, objectives and research questions

The aim of the proposed three year study (October 2023 – October 2026) is to:

- 1) Develop and verify a model framework suitable for assessing exposure of residents to pesticides applied using sideways and upward spraying techniques and
- 2) assess the exposure to pesticides for persons living in close vicinity to agricultural land on which pesticides are (intensively) applied via these techniques.

The study aim can be translated into the following three research questions:

1. How well can we predict exposure to residents living in close vicinity to fields where active substances are applied via sideways and upward spraying?
2. What are concentration levels of active substances of pesticides in the outdoor and indoor environment of homes located near orchards?
3. What is the individual exposure of residents living in close vicinity to fields where active substances are sprayed via sideways and upward spraying techniques?
4. What is the spatial variability in exposure to active substances sprayed via sideways and upward spraying techniques across different areas in the Netherlands?

Design and methods

Sideways and upward spraying techniques are used on fruit bushes, fruit trees, vines, hops and some types of nursery trees. In order to obtain a sound assessment of residents' exposures to active substances and sufficient data for model verification, a large number of samples, collected within a well-designed sampling frame, are needed. The study design therefore foresees collection of data regarding emission strength of pesticides and their active substances from fields, outdoor air concentrations, indoor dust concentrations and finally biomonitoring of persons living in close vicinity to selected crops. Selected households will be those residing within pre-defined distance categories to the fields (0 – 50m, 50 – 100m, 100 – 250m, 250 - 500m). A control group will be selected living more than 1km from agricultural cultivation areas. Deterministic and statistical models will be used to interpret the monitoring results of the study and extrapolate this research, allowing for the estimation of exposure to active substances in situations for which no measurements are available.

Expected results

The expected results of the project are:

- Descriptive statistics (means and percentiles) on measured environmental concentrations and personal exposures to active substances near locations where sideways and upward spraying is being applied.

- Verification of a modeling framework for estimation of residential exposure to pesticides sprayed via sideways and upward techniques.
- Maps of estimated residential exposure in the Netherlands via sideways, upward and/or boom spraying techniques. For identified active substances of relevance to other WPs.

Planned products

The project, which is a follow-up of the OBO project ([OBO 2019](#)), will deliver detailed measurements and an open-source model framework which can be used for estimating population exposures to current-use and newly introduced pesticides. The project will be carried out between March 2024 until October 2026).

Analysis of choices made and of remaining uncertainties

An explicit choice has been made to have an integrative work plan combining environmental and biological monitoring with modelling of exposures. Such an integrative approach is deemed necessary as to ensure the project delivers tangible and interpretable results. A similar approach was employed in phase 1 of OBO, with successful results.

3 Introduction and motivation

In general, exposure to pesticides via inhalation is considered to be an important route of exposure for people close to agricultural fields, in addition to general 'background' dietary exposures. In the phase 1 of the OBO project, researchers addressed residential environmental exposure coming from boom spraying applications. However, the model developed within phase 1, named OBO modelling framework (see [Figueiredo et al. 2022a](#)), was solely verified for downward spraying. Currently, there is a limited number of verified models for exposure assessment regarding sideways and upwards directed spraying. For example, there is the EU-harmonized EFSA OPEX model, however, this model is intended for another purpose, i.e. the predictive exposure assessment in the context of the supported uses for authorization of active substances and plant protection products.

The use of a verified model is important given that it is not feasible to measure exposure levels of all residents living close to agricultural lands and to all used pesticides in the Netherlands. Hence, verification of the exposure modelling of sideways and upwards application techniques would allow to include almost all spraying techniques used in the Netherlands into the exposure assessment. This would reduce exposure misclassification for homes close (within 500 meters) to agricultural fields where these techniques are commonly used (e.g. fruit crops and tree cultivation). These are about 5% of the homes in the Netherlands. Finally, such model can then be applied to extrapolate exposure assessment to a broader range of substances used in agriculture, and to the whole population.

Personal (individual) and environmental measurements will be done in homes located in the vicinity to crops where sideways and/or upward spraying occur (from very close vicinity to a distance of about 500m) and in a control group further away (> 1km). These measurements will provide information regarding actual exposure levels of the residents, but also on factors that influence exposure levels. Such factors include for example distance of the place of residence to the agricultural land, but also chemical characteristics of the pesticide, application techniques and meteorological conditions.

In the end, WP2 will produce environmental exposure maps to a broader range of substances used in agriculture. These maps will be linked to different health outcomes for different WPs (WP3 to WP8). It is important to stress that the epidemiological analyses in these WPs is limited to rural populations. The set of pesticides to simulate at national scale will be defined in those WPs based on the specific health outcome and a-priori information regarding exposure-health relationship. Moreover, WP2 will also produce additional information regarding possible exposure determinants that are not included in the deterministic modelling framework, and which, if proven relevant, can be included in future work.

4 Aim, objectives and research questions

It is simply not feasible to measure long-term exposure levels of all residents living close to agricultural lands where sideways and upward spraying occur, or to all used pesticides. Therefore, a study design has been selected that combines measurements of persons' exposure levels to pesticides (using biomonitoring) with external measurement and exposure models in order to be able to achieve reliable exposure estimates to active substances of the population in the Netherlands. The current study design follows closely the protocol of the phase 1 ([Figueiredo et al. 2021a](#)). Here, WP2 builds upon the lessons learned to adjust certain procedures of the previously setup protocol.

Personal and environmental measurements will be done in 100 homes located in the vicinity to crops where sideways and/or upward spraying occur (from very close vicinity to a distance of about 500m). These measurements will provide information regarding actual exposure levels of the residents, but also on factors that influence exposure levels. Such factors include for example distance of the place of residence to the agricultural land, but also chemical characteristics of the pesticide, application techniques and meteorological conditions. Measurement will also be conducted in ~10 controls living > 1 km from agricultural fields.

Existing models that calculate transport and fate of active substances and predict how these environmental concentrations lead to personal exposure of residents, will be calibrated and/or verified using the measurement results, and the additional information collected during the measurements (the factors that influence exposure levels, e.g. dietary intake) will be studied in order to identify possible (additional) exposure determinants. Such *integrated model frameworks* can then be applied to extrapolate exposure assessment to a broader range of substances used in agriculture, and to the whole population.

The study aim can be summarized into the following main research questions:

- i) How well can we predict exposure to residents living in close vicinity to fields where active substances are applied via sideways and upward spraying?
- ii) What are concentration levels of active substances of pesticides in the outdoor and indoor environment of homes located near orchards?
- iii) What is the individual exposure of residents living in close vicinity to fields where active substances are sprayed via sideways and upward spraying techniques?
- iv) What is the spatial variability in exposure to active substances sprayed via downward, sideways and upward spraying techniques across different areas in the Netherlands?

Information about exposure levels and sources as well as routes can ultimately be used to provide input in authorization procedures for pesticides, epidemiological studies, and if applicable, to estimate the effect of existing and future exposure mitigation strategies on population exposures. However, although their importance is recognized, authorization procedures and mitigation strategies fall outside the scope of the exposure study.

Finally, for the current study, the verification of the model for sideways and upwards spraying and creation of nation-wide exposure estimates is the central aim. The results of WP2 will serve as input for most of the remaining work packages in order to assign pesticide (only professional use) exposures to individuals, and consequently to evaluate possible effects on health.

5 Design and methods

Section 5.1 gives an overall description of the study protocol. Section 5.2 to 5.8 provide outlines and details of the different components of the protocol.

Henceforth we define areas that include both participating farms and participating residents as locations.

5.1 Study protocol

5.1.1 Measuring campaign

We will perform an exposure assessment strategy across all study locations, where environmental sampling will be complemented with biomonitoring and collection of contextual information (e.g. on land and pesticide use).

The study is centered around a large area where pesticides are regularly sprayed via sideways and/or upward spraying. In this area, a number of homes (n=75) are sampled twice at multiple locations (4 in total). Participants are recruited at various distances from agricultural fields (see below selection of study participants) so as to measure the direct contribution of spray drift, evaporation, and transfer to homes, and to establish regional and national background levels. Environmental sampling, namely outdoor air and indoor household dust, personal sampling (urine and wristbands) and the collection of contextual information (e.g. meteorological conditions, or activities of study participants that may be related to exposure levels, such as diet) will be performed on all selected study locations during the spraying season and outside the spraying season (i.e. when selected pesticides are no longer going to be applied until the next season). Finally, in one of the five locations, additional environmental sampling will be performed at a closer distance from the field, namely at 7.5 meters from the last tree row. This additional distance, which is not bound to a participating home, will provide additional data for model verification regarding airborne drift.

General procedure and data collection

During the spray season, the start of the measurements in one location is initiated by a specific spraying event (initiating event) and also depending on participants availability. We then collect exposure measurements using active air samplers for four consecutive days. Dust measurements are collected using a vacuum cleaner one week after the initiating event. Urine collection will take place the day after the initiating event. We will collect each individual's first morning void on the first and second day. It has been previously seen that given most pesticide fast metabolization, the first two days are the best window to capture exposure (if it occurs) from a spraying event. Measurements in control homes will be done in parallel. Contextual information will be collected, amongst others by asking participants to keep a diary on lifestyle factors, food consumption, activities, and observed spraying events. Records of pesticide application (time and type of a used pesticide on a specific field) will be collected from farmers with fields nearby the participating households after the measurement campaign.

Outside spraying season, the measuring campaign is similar to as described above, with two differences: 1) there is no initiating event to trigger the measuring campaign, so the start mainly depends on participants availability and 2) air measurements will be limited to one day. The reasoning for this is that inter-day exposure variability was minimal in this period during OBO-1. Figure X, illustrates the sampling campaign during spraying season and outside spraying season.

Finally, in order to provide information on background exposures (i.e. pesticide concentrations that occur in the natural environment due to e.g. combinations of long-range transport and persistence), we will use data collected in control homes (located further away from fields).

Analysis

Urine and Environmental samples (except the PUF-PAS) that link to known pesticides applications will be analyzed for the list of pre-selected pesticides and certain metabolites (see 5.6). In urine, pesticide biomarkers of exposure (in some cases the parent pesticide, more often a metabolite) will be measured as far as the analytical reference standard of the biomarker is available. Summary statistics on all collected samples will provide information on exposure of residents to selected pesticides within the study locations.

5.1.2 Modelling

OBO integrated modelling framework

The modelling framework developed under phase 1 of OBO will be adapted into R programming and simplifications on the input (e.g. reduction on parameters needed) will be studied in order to facilitate simulations at national scale for all fields, while maintaining model reliability. The Spexus model (Holterman et al. 2017) will be added to the framework in order to simulate spray drift from sideways and upward spraying. Finally, the full model framework will be verified against measured pesticides concentration in air and dust for the 4 locations included.

SPEXUS model verification

Spray drift models have previously been developed to assess droplet drift to the environment. In OBO-I we used IDEFICS model to calculate droplet drift from boom spraying applications. Here, we will be using the SPEXUS model, which is an empirical model based on 20 years of experimental data with verification against measured on field-deposits. However, in order for the model to be used or extrapolated to a framework for environmental exposure assessment of residents it needs to be verified against measured airborne pesticide concentrations.

5.2 Selection procedure of area and locations

In the proposal phase of the project, a few key areas across the Netherlands were identified where sideways and upward spraying occur. As shown in Figure 1 Panel A, Gelderland, Limburg and Zeeland have higher number of cultivations (per surface area) where sprayings using either sideways or upward techniques occur. There are some other visible small agglomerates of the selected cultivations in Noord-Holland, Utrecht and Flevoland.

Figure 1. Crops where upward and sideways spraying is used. (Data from 2021)

After calculating the number of homes within 500 meters from all crops where these spraying techniques are used, we identified the Betuwe (in Gelderland) as the area with most homes within 500 meters from crops (see Panel B, Figure 1). This area makes it more likely to identify sufficient

number of participants within a smaller area, which will facilitate immensely logistically as distances become smaller. Hence, we chose this area for our study.

The main objective will be to get enough participating farms and residents across 4 locations in this area, while aiming to have participating farms more isolated from other farms. This is to avoid capturing primary and secondary drift from other farms (i.e. disentangle exposure contributors), which would make model verification more challenging.

Also the required number of residents and their location with regard to the fields can be an argument to choose a specific location.

5.2.1 *Selection of crops*

Sideways and upward spraying are used in fruit orchards and tree cultivation. However, the hectares of fruit orchards in the Netherlands is higher. Therefore, the study will focus on these crops. Location of fruit orchards is available from the BRP Gewaspercelen datasets, which become available in the fall of a respective year.

5.2.2 *Selection of study locations based on crops*

In the context of this study, we denominate with a "study location" a cluster of residential buildings that are placed within short distance of an agricultural field (or cluster of agricultural fields) where fruit trees and bushes are grown (fruit orchards). Study locations will be selected using available maps (in particular yearly maps of crops, as well as cadastral data of all residential buildings) as a basis. A selection criterion is the presence of several potentially participating households within short distances (<500 m) of the selected crop, preferably downwind (using the predominant wind direction) of the respective field(s). The selection of downwind homes is to increase information that is useful for model verification, since if the wind is blowing away from the home we will not capture drift.

Residences will be selected that are located at different distances (see 5.1.1) to a field with the crops of interest.

5.2.3 *Selection of addresses based on locations*

For the selected locations, all residential addresses will be extracted using cadastral data. From these addresses, potential participants will be recruited. Addresses (relating to residential buildings) will be selected that are located at different distance categories to a field with the crops of interest: Selected addresses will be within distance categories of the fields at 0 – 50m, 50 – 100m, 100 –250m and 250-500m. Because the Netherlands is a very densely populated country, we expect that selecting places of residence within such short distances of fields will be unproblematic.

The pre-specified distance categories are based on the previous project (OBO-1), where a decrease in concentrations was seen with distance from boom spraying applications ([Figueiredo et al. 2021b](#)). We hypothesize that direct exposure is less important after the 250m distance. However, since sideways and upward spraying have likely higher drift than boom spraying (downward), we decided to add one more category (250-500m) in OBO-2.

Note that a household can have one distance to one field but the same household can also be in proximity to multiple other fields or orchards. By using the verified OBO-2 modelling framework we will be able to account for multiple fields, based on available crop registry data and farmers information on pesticide usage on these crops.

5.3 **Selection procedure of participants**

Participants of the field study will be local residents, farmers/contractors and their family members, and controls. Farmers are often the users of pesticides. However, in some cases, they and their family members can be classified as residents.

5.3.1 *Definition of a 'resident'*

In this study, a resident is defined as follows:

- a person who lives in proximity to agricultural land on which fruit trees or bushes are grown that are treated with pesticides;
- in proximity = within 500 m from the perimeter of a treated field;

5.3.2 *Target groups*

In WP2 we aim to include adults (18-59y) and also potty-trained children and adolescents (>2-18y) if they also live in a participating home. The criteria is to include at least one adult per home. Within this group we will collect detailed demographic information and time-activity data. This allows for other groupings by for instance gender, time-at-home, etcetera. This is different than OBO-1, where non-potty trained children were also invited to participate. However, as a lesson learned from OBO, we saw that including non-potty trained children in the target group made it more difficult to find suitable participants and also required a different urine sample collection approach (diaper method). Moreover, questionnaire information was more often lacking for children (even if the parent where the ones writing it down).

5.3.3 *Selection of participants*

Potential study participants will be contacted based on the extracted addresses: Residents will receive an invitation letter and information about the study by postal mail. If they are interested in participating, they will be requested to return a completed registration form. Those who express their interest will be interviewed by phone using a structured interview script to check if they fulfil the inclusion criteria. This script has been developed in OBO. Only one adult (aged ≥ 18 years) from each household will be asked to participate, with the exception for homes where farmers live. Here, exposure can be significantly different between household members, so a partner will be also asked to participate (see 5.3.4).

Subjects will be excluded in the case of inability to understand the questionnaires and informed consent procedure. Each study participant will sign an informed consent form.

5.3.4 *Selection of farmers*

Potential farmers will not be approached by a letter first but directly by phone, because a personal approach increases the chance that they will participate in the research. Telephone numbers can be collected through existing stakeholder organizations and personal contacts. After first contact an information leaflet will be provided to the farmers in order for him/her/they to have a clear understanding of the project aims.

After this, and based on the consultation of regional/agricultural experts, a selection is made of farmers on appropriate locations who might be positive about participation in the research and meet the selection criteria. They will be contacted by telephone.

The main criteria for selection is that the farmer grows fruit trees in the Betuwe area.

5.3.5 *Farmer families*

If a farmer lives on or near the selected fields the household will be deemed suitable and one adult resident will be invited to participate. The statistical analysis will take into account if a person belongs to a farmer family or not.

Inclusion of farmers as participants will also have an added value to WP9, which will focus on feasibility of occupational exposure studies to pesticides.

5.3.6 *Controls*

In addition to residents living in proximity to orchards, also 20 persons with likely lower exposures from spraying (comparison participants) will be included in the study. These are participants living in households located 1) >1 km from agricultural fields and 2) in either a mildly urban area (i.e. smaller towns, 1000-1500 homes per km²), hardly urban (i.e. villages, 500-1000 homes per km²) or rural (less than 500 per km²). Controls will receive an invitation letter and information about the study by mail. If they are interested in participating, the same procedure to include them into the study will apply as for all other participants. We aim to include controls from the same region as residents.

5.4 Data collection and sample bank

Table 1 summarizes the different matrices that will be sampled, the sampling method, and their relevance. Table 2 summarizes the contextual data that will be collected.

Different types of samples were taken in phase 1 of OBO. Out of these, we identified 4 types of sampling methods as key to explain exposure variability across time and space and useful for model verification (see [Figueiredo 2022a](#)). These methods (see table 2) were selected to be used in OBO-2. We decided not to include soil, home garden vegetables and handwipes as it was shown in phase 1 that these matrixes added little value in comparison with the selected list. The selected methods include urine collection, sampling of floor dust using a vacuum cleaner, sampling air using a high volume sampler, and wristband deployment.

Table 1. Overview of samples to be collected

Type of sample	Represents	Relevance
Biological monitoring (Human)		
Urine	Short term exposure	(Proxy for) internal exposure (in ng/L) (all exposure routes)
Personal External		
Wristbands	Short to long term exposure (time that participants wear the wristbands)	proxy for inhalation and dermal exposure (in ng/g);
Indoor environment		
Vacuumed Floor Dust	Short to long term exposure	Proxy for cumulative exposure for dust ingestion and dermal contact (in ng/g)
Outdoor environment		
High volume sampler (adsorption tube, filter)	Short term exposure (during time of sample collection)	proxy for inhalation exposure (in ng/m ³);
Passive air sampler (PUF-PAS)	Long term exposure (during time of sample collection)	Proxy for environmental exposure (in ng/g PUF)

Table 2. Contextual data collected in the different measurement protocols

Variable	Method
Professional pesticide use	Farm management system or pesticide registration
Details on application from farmers	Registration forms
Details on urine collection	Diary
Demographic characteristics	Questionnaire
Life style	Diary / Questionnaire
Time activity patterns	Diary
Pesticide use at home	Diary
Diet, specifically consumption of home-grown produce and organic food	Diary
Meteorological conditions	Closest KNMI meteo station*

* In order to verify the developed exposure model, meteo data will be collected with an in-situ station at the location where repeated measurements will occur.

As approved in OBO phase1 protocol, The Institute for Risk Assessment Sciences (IRAS) will manage the sample bank for the duration of the study. The individual samples will be stored at Wageningen Food Safety Research (biobank and environmental sample bank) until analyses are completed, and remaining samples will be stored at the central sample bank at IRAS. The sample bank is property of IRAS. The sample bank is available for future research but can only be accessed with written permission of IRAS and for human urine samples only for what was indicated in the informed consent.

5.5 Sample size calculation

Based on the power calculations of OBO phase 1 and the results from that study, we concluded that for phase 2 we should aim to include 100 participants from different households. For each participant, both biological and environmental samples will be collected.

5.6 Pesticide selection and chemical analysis of samples

In order to select which pesticides to analyze we proceeded with a selection based on several criteria. The most important being that these are (anticipated to be) sprayed on fruit trees, namely apples and pears, as they cover the most acreage. The different criteria are as follows: 1) the pesticide is used and allowed in at least one of the cultivations of interest (apples and/or pears), since these fruit crops have the most acreage; 2) product authorization only expires end 2024 or later (or re-approval is foreseen), given that the measuring campaign will occur in 2025. 3) the pesticide is only authorized to be used between February and October in fruit trees (i.e. most frequent spraying period – CTGB distribution). This will guarantee a clear distinction between spraying season and outside spraying season. 4) pesticides that are only allowed for professional use. This is to avoid capturing other exposures aside from the spraying in agricultural fields. 5) the pesticide is sprayed sideways and/or upward. These are the spraying techniques not yet verified in the modelling framework, hence the focus should be on pesticides sprayed using one or both of these techniques. 6) the pesticide chemical analysis should be amenable to one multi-residue method with reasonable sensitivity and existing protocols and reference materials.

The following table (Table 3) shows the results for the above selection for environmental analysis.

Table 3. Selection of pesticides for environmental analysis.

Fungicide	Insecticide
boscalid	abamectine
boscalid-OH metabolite	acequinocyl
bupirimate	acetamiprid
captan*	acetamiprid-N-desmethyl
cyflufenamid	chlorantraniliprole
difenoconazole	cyantraniliprole
difenoconazole-OH metabolite	cyflumetofen
dodine	flonicamid
fludioxonil	indoxacarb
fludioxonil-OH metabolite	pirimicarb
fluopyram	pyriproxyfen
fluopyram- benzamide	spirodiclofen-enol

fluxapyroxad	spirodiclofen
folpet*	spirotetramat
kresoxim-methyl	spirotetramat-enol
penconazole	
penthiopyrad	
pyraclostrobin	
pyrimethanil	
pyrimethanil- OH metabolite	
tebuconazole	
tebuconazole-OH metabolite	
trifloxystrobin	
trifloxystrobin-acid metabolite	

* Analyzed with a separate method;

For our study, the above list, which includes both parent compounds and metabolites, is final and will not be reduced. However, given that some substances that are not on the list can be analyzed also via multi-method, the list might be slightly extended if information becomes known about the importance of including one or more compounds. It is important to stress that for captan and folpet the analytical method is different than all other substances and hence an additional sample needs to be collected to analyze these two compounds. Stakeholders, the sounding board and the scientific advisory board may be consulted about the final selection of plant protection products.

For biological analysis, we will try to include as many biologically relevant parent compounds and/or metabolites of the pesticides indicated in Table 3, as long as the analytical standards are available. For example, for captan and folpet, this would be PHI and THPI metabolites.

Every selection will have limitations. Therefore, the sample bank with remaining environmental and urine samples potentially allows for future assessment of those substances that are not selected or could not be measured under the current methodologies.

The chemical analysis will be done by one laboratory with vast experience in pesticide analysis across different matrices, namely, Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR).

5.6.1 Analytical methods

Environmental samples

For the determination of the active substances in samples taken in the environment (e.g. air and household dust), state-of-the-art instrumental methods will be used. Liquid chromatography combined with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) will be the method of choice for almost all selected pesticides (Table 3). For analysis of captan and folpet a separate method using gas chromatography will be used.

Samples will be extracted using a suitable extraction solvent and procedure, which may differ depending on the physico-chemical properties of the analyte and the matrix. If required, extracts will be cleaned in order to achieve sufficient selectivity and sensitivity, and to improve robustness of the instrumental analysis.

Urine analysis

Urine analysis will focus on biomarkers of exposure of the pesticides included in the environmental analysis, as far as the analytical reference standards are available and the biomarkers are amenable to the same multi-biomarker method based on LC-MS/MS. Sample preparation, besides extraction and cleanup, may involve a deconjugation step to convert multiple metabolites into one

form for which the analytical reference standard is available. Due to the more extensive sample preparation and the limitations in availability of analytical reference standards, the possibilities for simultaneous quantitative determination of multiple metabolites in urine is limited compared to the environmental analysis.

5.6.2 *Validation and quality control*

In order to ensure acceptability of analytical results to the different stakeholders, method validation and quality control procedures will be based on internationally accepted guidelines for the determination of substances in agricultural and environmental commodities [SANTE/11312/2021v2].

5.7 **Extrapolation of study results**

Due to practical considerations, only a limited number of situations will be studied, i.e. a limited number of substances, exposure situations, environmental conditions and residents. Consequently, the study results have to be generalized and extrapolated to cover other pesticides, crops and applications, for residents and the population as a whole and by sub-categories of the population according to age, gender, etcetera, if necessary). In other words, it has to be determined how the exposure levels in the studied situation rank with respect to exposure levels of the population (residents, general population).

To address the above, measurement data will be used to calibrate and increase the verification status of the deterministic models. The models will then be used to extrapolate this research to other pesticides and other locations, allowing for the estimation of exposure to pesticides in situations for which no measurements have been carried out. These models consist of mathematical and empirical descriptions of processes of emission (e.g. volatilization), dispersion of droplets, gases and particles and exposure (i.e. inhalation and dust ingestion). The work carried here will largely be based upon the existing OBO modelling framework (see [Figueiredo et al. 2022a](#)), verified already for boom spraying applications. Information about physico-chemical properties of pesticides, application techniques, and cultivation characteristics on one hand, and meteorological conditions, location of houses and human physiology and activities on the other hand serve as input for these models.

5.7.1 *Integration of droplet model for sideways and upward spraying*

In first instance we will study the use of the SPEXUS model ([Holtermann et al. 2018](#)) for calculation of pesticide drift from sideways and upward spraying. The model will be verified against measured air concentration data collected during the study. We chose real-life setting verification to capture actual spray dynamics, intending to place pumps in the predominant wind direction with provisions for repeats in one location.

Modelled air concentrations will be compared to measure air concentrations (active sampling), we will then derive two important metrics, which are Root-mean square error and R2, to inform us on the accuracy of the model and also how well we explain spatial variability. The modelled values, as well as the measured, will be compared with urinary biomarker measurements. However, in this last comparison, as seen in OBO-1, we don't expect necessarily a strong agreement, since we are only focusing on improving the environmental exposure estimates and urine takes also into account dietary exposure.

In order for contextual and other pertinent information to be collected for model verification, a complete list of what is sprayed by farmers will be compiled. Besides this list, data on the pesticides chemical characteristics, spraying techniques, crop growth stage and meteorological conditions will also be collected from different data sources.

5.7.2 *Extrapolation and open-source*

In a second step we will update the OBO modelling framework by including a meta-model from IDEFICS (used for boom spraying) and SPEXUS in the open-source R framework. The integral model framework will be verified using the existing outdoor air and indoor dust data either as independent validation sets or by cross-validation. Subsequently, performance indicators such as

spearman rank correlation and kappa coefficients between modelled and observed exposures can be calculated to estimate the models' ability to correctly estimate spraying-related exposure of participants.

The choice of using metamodels is based on the fact that, as seen in OBO-1, running IDEFICS is intensive and not feasible for all the Netherlands. A meta-model is a representation of the relationships between input and output from the IDEFICS and SPEXUS models. Hence, based on different inputs provided a-priori to both models, we can derive several different outputs and build a relationship (e.g. a regression) that represents the model.

The integral model framework should be able to support calculation of environmental exposure by combining use patterns of pesticides with (elementary) properties and environmental conditions. In particular, the final integral model framework will enable us to estimate spraying-related residential exposure to active substances in the Netherlands.

5.7.2 Sensitivity analyses

During WP2 we will do two simulations, as it was done also in OBO-1, simulating the participating fields and also simulating all fields within 500m from participating homes. These results proved to be important before as the inclusion of multiple fields led to modelled values to be closer to the measured values, while one single field simulation led to underestimation of exposure. Some input parameters, such as application rate, pesticide properties and wind conditions during spraying, can have a large influence in the model outcome. For this, at the end of WP2, when producing national exposure maps, we will take into account variability in these parameters by performing monte-carlo simulations and get a distribution of exposure instead of a single value.

5.8 General communication

Communication will be performed in close connection with WP10 and the sounding board.

Effective communication is more than a simple one-way transfer of information. Communication needs to address public and stakeholders concerns and facilitate a productive and meaningful interaction between actors from different backgrounds and with diverging interests. Research has demonstrated that effective mutual communication is one of the key challenges in risk governance.

Effective communication is essential from the start till the end of this study: i.e. from recruitment of the study population till the framing of the message on the outcomes of the study. Effective communication means accommodating the communication to the information needs and the attitude of different stakeholders (residents, farmers/growers, civil society and policymakers). It means a key message with the right tone of voice and comprehensible terminology and tools that are used and understood by stakeholders. Managing the expectations on the outcomes of the study (e.g. measuring spraying-related exposure to pesticides instead of measuring health risks of pesticides) will also be an important area of concern for the communication.

The communication is targeted at the participants and the stakeholder groups.

To successfully communicate about the research and its results to these stakeholders, specific knowledge is indispensable. We therefore define a twofold aim in our communication strategy:

- The communication on the study and its outcomes is accommodated to the knowledge, attitude and expectations of the primary, secondary and tertiary stakeholders.
- Consensus and clear agreements on the implementation of the communication strategy of all parties in the consortium of this study. All partners need to abide to the agreed key message, use the same terminology and commit themselves to the planning and coordination of the external communication.

6 Observational study field protocol for environmental and biomonitoring sampling

The overall measurement campaign aims at including 4 locations with approximately 20 households each. For each household one adult is included. This sampling scheme follows residents outside the spraying season and during the spraying season. The measuring campaign starts outside the spraying season (October to December 2024) in order to setup a baseline background measurement. The measuring campaign in the spraying season will occur in 2025 (March to August).

Protocol for environmental and personal sampling

Outside Spraying season

- Sampling protocol will start based on participants availability, as no sprayings will be occurring.
- Environmental measurements will be performed in the same 4 locations as during spraying season. The environmental measurements include outdoor air sampling and settled house dust sampling via floor vacuuming. Settled dust will be collected at the end of a one week period. Outdoor air sampling will be performed for two days.
- The personal measurements include wristband, worn for seven consecutive days, and morning urine void collected in two consecutive days.
- Due to budgetary reasons, wristbands will only be analyzed for people living within 250m from fields and also controls.
- Repeated measurements will not be done outside spraying season, as there is no model verification here.

During Spraying season

- Sampling protocol will start at the time a grower reports an intended use (= application).
- Environmental measurements will be performed in 4 locations. The environmental measurements include outdoor air sampling and settled house dust sampling via floor vacuuming. Settled dust will be collected at the end of a one week period following the application event. Outdoor air sampling will be performed daily for four consecutive days.
- The personal measurements include wristband, worn for seven consecutive days, and morning urine void collected one day after the spraying (day 1) and following day (day2).
- In one out of the 4 locations, additional active air sampling will be performed at different periods and at an additional distance (adjacent to field). This is setup in order to capture crop growth stage to support SPEXUS model verification, including an added local (micro)meteorological measurement device.
- In this protocol also a control group consisting of approximately 20 households will be established. The households in the control group are selected in rural areas but without cultivations in the nearby vicinity.
- Due to budgetary reasons, wristbands will only be analyzed for people living within 250m from fields and also controls.

In Table 3 the number of samples per sampling technique and per season that will be collected are presented.

Table 3: Number of collected samples and homes per sampling technique and season.

	During spraying season		Outside spraying season		Total collected
	Residents	Controls	Residents	Controls	
Outdoor air sampling	238* (55)	40 (20)	110 (55)	40 (20)	428
Vacuumed floor dust	55 (55)	20 (20)	55 (55)	20 (20)	150

Wristbands	80 (80)	20 (20)	80 (80)	20 (20)	200
Urine (morning void)	160 (80)	40 (20)	160 (80)	40 (20)	400
PUF-PAS**	55 (55)	20 (20)	-	-	75**

Number of samples (number of homes); *including 3 repeated measurements at 3 separate distances in one location. ** PUF-PAS will be deployed in parallel with active air samplers and also between non-spraying and spraying season.

Short description environmental and personal sampling methods

Active air sampling method for outdoor air sampling

Given the circumstances (i.e. data for verification of model outcome) and the expected concentrations, we will be using high volume samplers (flow ~100m³ per day, ng/m³ range or less, sampling during 24hours). Given that we are interested in total pesticide concentration we will measure pesticide concentrations in the gas-phase + particle-phase, using PM10 filters and absorbents like XAD-2 resin. This method is similar to OBO-1. After every 24-hours, the sampler inlet switches, this is done consecutively during a four day period.

Indoor sampling method for dust sampling

Here, two techniques were employed previously: a) the use of vacuuming to collect dust from a a-priori defined area and room and b) the use of a clean doormat to trap dust particles. In OBO-1, it was concluded that vacuuming floor dust was more appropriate to capture longer term exposure, while the doormats captured shorter time windows of exposure. Also, the floor dust captured an accumulation of multiple sources, where doormats were predominantly capturing take-home route (i.e. shoes and pets walking pass the doormat) and also dust deposition. Given the above we chose to collect floor dust in WP2. By having dust collected one-week after the spraying event we guarantee to capture long-term accumulation + the week of measuring (which includes farmers sprayings). We will not ask participants to vacuum clean prior, since the dust matrix will serve as proxy to inform us about long-term exposure and not acute exposure.

Urine sampling

First morning void urine samples will be collected according to standard procedures. Upon receipt at the laboratory, the urine will be aliquoted and stored in an ultrafreezer (-80°C) until analysis.

Wristbands

Silicone wristbands are a relatively novel tool to measure multiple chemicals with a low cost and non-invasive personal method. It is a passive sampling device that can be used for 1 week or longer, depending on the exposure time-window of interest. Pre-cleaned silicone wristbands (one size, 20cm), will be supplied directly to field coordinators. Here, wristbands will be worn for one week as it was shown in previous studies that this is sufficient time to capture several pesticides and reach equilibrium with the environment. Wristbands are mostly used for personal pesticide mixture assessment and will serve to understand the different mixtures each individual is exposed to and whether these are also present in urine, air and/or dust. They provide a qualitative measure and a proxy for environmental exposure, since they can be used to differentiate between low and high exposed. The wristbands have proven to capture inhalation and dermal exposure.

Passive air sampling method (PUF-PAS) for outdoor air sampling

The PUF-PAS is a smaller and cheaper alternative to active air sampling. The polyurethane passive air sampler consists of two metal disks with a matrix of polyurethane foam in between. Pesticides can partition from the air into the matrix at a certain rate. After a certain deployment time the PUF-PAS can be retrieved and the contents of the matrix can be analysed in the lab, providing a semi-quantitative results (amount pesticide per PUF weight). The PUFs will be used in parallel to the active samplers to study their performance as an air sampling measuring device. They will also be deployed between spraying and non-spraying season, which is a transition as some applications might still occur.

7 Logistics, field implementation and results

The project requires detailed planning, preparation, organization and execution of a field study. We included the necessary field coordination both towards farmers (partners CLM and WUR) and to residents (partner IRAS). To enable the conduct of sampling across different locations, a dedicated field team will be established encompassing all required expertise. The field team will be directed by one central coordinator who is responsible for the coordination of the field work, including the recruitment of participants.

The aim of this section is to provide efficient information regarding the coordination of all the practical fieldwork of the project as summarized in section 5 and 6. The aim is to achieve well-tuned field activities and logistics and ethically acceptable involvement (psychological and physical load) of participants (local residents and farmers). This will lead, as seen in OBO-1, to motivation and consent of participants during the whole study, feasible research and trustworthy results.

This protocol encompasses three key points:

1. Extend the ongoing fieldwork protocol of OBO-1. Already approved by the Medical Research Ethics Committee (METC)
2. Prepare and execute the recruitment of participants (local residents and farmers)
3. Coordinate and organize the fieldwork.

7.1 Ethical review board (METC) and data protection impact assessment (DPIA)

METC

Both the details of the monitoring protocol, and the recruitment method were already reviewed and approved by the Medical Research Ethics Committee (METC) for OBO-1. The METC reviews and judges whether the medical-ethical scientific research involving human suspects is in line with the Medical Research Act (WMO).

Given that the sampling methods and used protocols here are similar to OBO-1, WP2 will revise again the documentation submitted and when no changes are needed, the METC can be extended to this project.

At the start of the research a monitor will be appointed to safeguard the procedures during the whole project in accordance to the WMO and the Personal Data Protection Act (Wbp).

DPIA

Under the new EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) legislation, a DPIA is needed. This is a process designed to identify and minimize the risks associated with data protection of a project or system. Several steps will be taken in order to carry out a Data Protection Impact Assessment. These are:

1. Identify and document the types of personal data we are processing, the purposes of the processing, and the parties involved.
2. Consult the data protection officers (DPOs), to guarantee that the different perspectives on the privacy implications are being processed.
3. Identify and assess the potential risks to participating individuals' rights and freedoms associated with the proposed activities.
4. Implement measures to mitigate the identified risks in point 3. This could involve changing processes, adopting privacy-enhancing technologies, or reassessing the necessity of certain data processing activities.
5. Keep a record of the DPIA process, including the outcomes of the risk assessment, the measures taken to mitigate risks, and any consultations with stakeholders.
6. Periodically review and, when necessary, update the DPIA, especially when there are changes to the proposed activities or new risks emerge.
7. Ensure that the DPIA is approved by UU data protection officers
8. Ensure that employees and other relevant parties are aware of data protection requirements and are trained to implement the necessary measures.

7.2 Recruitment of participants

Participants of the field study will be local residents, farmers/contractors and their family members, and controls. Farmers are often the users of pesticides. However, if farmers want to participate, they and their family members can be classified as local residents.

Farmers will also be informed about the work done in WP9 and asked whether they want to collaborate. WP9 is feasibility study that will solely focus on occupational exposure to pesticides.

Selection of potential participants

The target group and controls for the study and desired characteristics have been defined in section 5. Based on the selection of crops, active substances and locations the potential participants will be determined. The final choice of locations depends on whether suitable participants can be found at the locations.

Develop recruitment text, materials and information for participants

Directly at the first contact, management of expectations is important. Besides the specific agreements about how the study will be conducted and the personal contact during visits of researchers, more general information can be used to explain about the background of the study. To this end, we can use the following material developed in OBO-1:

Material for first introduction of the research to potential participants will be:

- Recruitment letter for residents;
- Telephone script for calling residents and farmers;
- Participants information leaflet: two different versions, for residents and for farmers.

The aim of the participants information leaflet is that (potential) residents and farmers become motivated to participate in the research and have a clear understanding of:

- The aim of the research • Methodology
- Everything that we will ask of the participants. This follows from the monitoring protocol.
- Feedback of results, including method and frequency of feedback
- Financial reimbursement
- Confidentiality
- Communication
- Contact persons

Contact person for participants is a researcher from the fieldwork research team. This person is in any case the first person to contact in case the participant has questions, concerns or remarks about the research.

Additionally, participants can contact the information desk and ask their questions about the research or report special circumstances by telephone.

Also a confidential and independent medical adviser (required by WMO / METC), not involved with the research, can be approached to give information about the reliability of the researchers and the (human) safety of the research.

A point of attention here is not only to formulate the communicated message carefully, but also to consider who the messenger should be.

c. Alignment and design of screening questionnaire

The screening questionnaire will be used to make a good selection of the participants (check whether they fit with the criteria). This questionnaire, developed and used in OBO-1, includes questions concerning the personal details of participants. These are questions about e.g. age, gender, weight, lifestyle (e.g. leisure activities), occupational and para-occupational exposure to pesticides (exposure via, for example, family members, who work with pesticides and live in the same home) and pesticides usage within the home (in garden, plants, or as biocides). Farmers will be asked about e.g. landownership and possible relation with (sub)tenants, who applies the

pesticides (farmer himself, contractor, employee, temporary employee), how availability and quality of data about pesticide application is, crops and application techniques.

The questionnaire also contains questions about contact and type of communication between farmer and local residents, history (media attention, politics), stakeholders involved (such as the district health service (GGD), Netherlands Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority (NVWA), Agricultural-Horticultural Organisations (LTO), residents' groups, NGOs and political parties) and the way in which residents are organized (possibly affiliated with a group that represents them). This information will be used later in order to develop an effective communication strategy.

d. Informed consent

Important elements of the informed consent are that the participants have had the possibility to ask questions and they received an explanation about situations of withdrawal from the research without notifying the reason.

In the form, farmers will be asked to confirm that they are willing to provide the study team with information concerning their pesticide usage.

Result of these activities are:

- A list of addresses of farmers and residents that fit the criteria to participate; - Several recruitment and information texts and materials (recruitment letter, telephone script, tailor made participant's information leaflet, prepared confidential medical counselor and an information telephone desk standby as soon as the field work starts;

For the general public, including people in the immediate surroundings of participants information material will be developed by RIVM; - A screening questionnaire; - An informed consent.

e. Expectation management

During recruitment of participants (local residents and controls) it is crucial that they clearly understand what the research will (not) bring them. It must be clear that the study will not answer the question of whether or not there is a health risk for the participating individuals. For example, certain substances (pesticides or the corresponding metabolites) could be detected in urine, while it is unknown whether this has health consequences for the participant. From the first contact, expectation management will be an important focus.

How

- Personal visit (intake interview) to explain the details of the study and personal significance of the measurements, to discuss expectations and conditions for participation. This results in signing *informed consent* form (see 7.2_d).

f. Recruitment period and distribution of responsibilities

The exact moment of the recruitment depends on the timing of protocol approval. Ideally, this will be done in June and July 2024.

By whom

The fieldwork team will carry out the recruitment. Eventually an exception can be made in the first telephone call with the farmers, when (in consultation of regional/agricultural experts) it is evident that recruitment will be more successful when the farmer is approached by a warm contact first. It is very important that recruitment is executed by people who know what occupies the participants and how they should deal with that in a good way (Van der Wal et al. 2011).

These activities result in sufficient, motivated and agreed participants, who comply with the selection criteria. Also a list of participants and characteristics is a deliverable.

7.3 Coordination and organization of the fieldwork

Based on the final agreements on the WP2 research protocol (this document), a logistic plan for the field activities will be prepared in more detail. Together with partners we will define how the activities can be efficiently organized, who is responsible for what and what the costs are. The plan contains:

- When, where and what technical devices should be placed;
- When samples and monitoring data should be collected;
- How and when transport is organized;
- What the maximum time is, between sampling/monitoring and analysis.

The resulting products of these activities are a broadly accepted and detailed monitoring protocol, an integrated and detailed fieldwork manual and a well elaborated logistic plan.

Internal organization

The field team will be directed by one central coordinator who is responsible for the coordination of the field work, including the recruitment of participants. A distinction is made between the coordination and alignment of the research in the field and the management of the contact with the participants. The central coordinator is therefore responsible for:

- Determining whether the monitoring protocol is being followed;
- Identifying possible constraints and reporting particularities;
- Mutual coordination (research team, WP2 partners) possible realignment (consider the effects of weather conditions or deviating behavior of farmers/local residents);
- Mutual communication and feedback.

Management of the contact with participants

It is important to build a trusting relationship with the participants. Following the intake interview, supervision and support of the participants will consist of the following:

- Announcing the start of the study;
- Announcing times, duration and person or persons who conduct the sampling;
- Communication and explanation during the sampling and during the period between samplings
- Feedback/evaluation following completion of the sampling;
- Feedback of results.

Formation and training of the field work team

The fieldwork during the spraying season will be determined by the activities of the farmer. During the spraying season, the fieldwork team should be stand-by 7 days a week, to be able to quickly respond to spray events that are usually announced at short notice. In this way, a notification can be dealt with quickly and adequately, in cases where immediate measurements are required.

A notification can be for example that a farmer reports (phone, sms, email): "I planned to spray tomorrow morning at 6 o'clock" or "I checked my decision support system (e.g. prediction infection periods fungi related to weather information) and I have to spray within one hour".

The team will contain experts who should have experience in dealing with questions about the research and how to carry out the sampling following the protocol.

These researchers will frequently have contact with the participants, visit them to collect samples and to respond to questions. They also are attainable by email and phone.

Before the study begins the team will be trained in communication and all the measurement techniques that will be used. Quality monitoring will take place by means of frequent feedback to the WP2-leader and by oversight of other involved partners.

At the end of each research year the approach and organization of the team will be evaluated.

Result of this activity is a qualified and well-prepared fieldwork team.

The field researcher

The field researcher will visit participants regularly, not only to collect information but also to maintain good relationships and to provide regular feedback on the progress of the study. Such engagement is very important to keep participants motivated, to collect reliable samples and information and because it helps to minimize attrition of study participants.

At the visit of the residents, the field researcher will collect the samples and diaries. Before taking the sample package, he/she/they will check that it contains the expected number of completed study packs and that in each study pack, the sample label on the diary matches that on the (urine) sample receptacle. The field researcher will check that the diaries have been fully and correctly completed and that the date and time of collection has been written on the (urine) sample receptacle.

A field researcher will also contact participating farmers on a regular basis to ensure continued participation, help partners in the collection of pesticide usage records and obtain updated information on their planned pesticide usage. At the last visit to the farm during a spraying season, the researcher will recheck the farmers spray records to ensure that details of all relevant spray periods have been recorded, including information relating to application rate, treated area, sprayer type, nozzle type, forward speed, water volume, crop height and other relevant parameters.

These activities result in an efficiently coordinated and organized field study, well-supported participating residents and farmers, and a well followed monitoring protocol.

7.4 Collection and setup of uniform database

The collection of data and samples of/at the participants is organized by the field coordinator. The following databases are examples and not all variables are here described.

Farmers spray records

A protected uniform database for farmers spray records will be created and will include:

- A form for record keeping by the farmers. Where possible and more efficient we explore if digital exchange of data with farm management programs is possible.
- Quality control of the data (uniform notation of pesticide names, check on extreme doses, etc)
- Collection of individual data into a central database and transformation of pesticide trade names towards active substances (split up pesticide with multiple substances, calculation of dose per active substance, etc).

Participants data

A uniform (password protected) database for residents and controls will be created and will include:

- Contact information (address, phone, email)
- Appointments made (year, month, day and hour)
- Additional relevant information (moving home, absent during certain period, ...)

Field work datasets

A uniform database for residents and controls will be created and will include:

- Checklist for samplers deployed and time of deployment
- Field worker observations on changes in surrounding environment (e.g. new buildings or planted trees that can influence somehow the sampling techniques used)

- Additional relevant information (e.g. sampler damaged, wristband worn less days, ...)
- ...

The result of this activity is a well-organized collection of data and samples (residents, farmers) and an uniform database of farmers pesticide use records.

7.5 Completion of the measuring campaign

Careful completion is important for the participants of the research. The field study will end early 2025 (outside spraying season). In 2025 and first half of 2026, WP2 will work on chemical analysis, statistical analysis, model verification and interpretation of the sampling and monitoring data and reporting. This means that participants will not receive any results of the research until the end of the project (September 2026). See section 7.6 for detailed planning.

This activity results in a management report and realistic expectations of the participants with regard to the follow-up, publications of the results of the study and their involvement in it.

7.6 Deliverables

WP2 deliverables (and their deadlines) were already setup (see Table 4):

Table 4: List of deliverables

Number	Deliverable name	Short description	Participant executing deliverable	Type	Delivery date
D2.1	Study protocol	Report on pesticide selection, study area and observational study field protocol	Utrecht University	Report	M7
D2.2	Observational study – an overview	Report on number of participants, demographics, contextual data and field related information (e.g. number of collected samples)	Utrecht University	Table	M24
D2.3	Chemical analysis	Analysis of environmental and human samples. Report on analytical methods used and analysis results obtained.	Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR)	Report	M27
D2.4	Descriptive statistics	Descriptive statistics of pesticides in measured samples	Utrecht University	Report	M30
D2.5	Verification of a modelling framework	Verification of a modelling framework for sideways and upward spraying, allowing for extrapolation to other locations, crops and pesticides	Utrecht University	Report	M32
D2.6	Residential exposure across the Netherlands	Modelled residential exposure to selected pesticides from sideways and upward spraying in the Netherlands	Utrecht University	Report	M36

7.7 Link between WP2 and consequent WPs

The collected data in WP2 will not directly inform the health studies. The data will be used to 1) verify the air and dust model for sideways and upward spraying techniques, 2) identify prevalent mixtures and 3) assess variability in exposure, both environmental, as well as individual (personal). WP2 will strive to improve environmental exposure assessment, by moving away from proxies, such as buffers or distance to closest fields, and calculating fate of pesticides from each field in the Netherlands and produce environmental exposure maps to a broader range of substances used in agriculture. The linkage between WP2 and others WPs is that these maps will be used to bring exposure to pesticides and different health outcomes.

It is important to stress that the set of pesticides to simulate at national scale will be defined in consequent WPs, not in WP2. This will be based on the specific health outcome and a-priori information regarding exposure-health relationship.

Finally, one additional likely output of WP2, as also seen in OBO-1, is the creation of more information regarding possible exposure determinants that are not included in the deterministic modelling framework, and which, if proven relevant, can be included. These can be done, for example, by building statistical models in which one the predictors is the outcomes of the deterministic framework.

8 Critical success factors and risks

8.1 Critical success factors

This part describes critical success factors (risks) and indicate go/no-go moments.

The following points are considered essential for the success of the project:

- Involvement and motivation of volunteer participants (residents);
- Good cooperation and willingness of farmers that apply the pesticides;
- Strong overall coordination;
- Skilled field work team in place;
- Good analytical methods which are sensitive enough to also measure low exposure levels;
- Use and/or (further) development of suitable dispersion and exposure models to extrapolate the measurement results to various environmental and application conditions, other pesticides, and target groups;
- Good cooperation and coherence among WP2 partners and consortium members;
- Room for adjustments of the work plan. Since the study is complex there need to be options to adapt certain aspects of the project if this is considered the best approach for success of the project;
- Good communication with all relevant stakeholders.

The following points are considered risks inherent to the project:

- Farmers at the selected study locations are aware of the study and as a result may alter their (spraying) behavior. Although it is quite certain this will happen to some extent, it is uncertain how much bias (compared to the uncontrolled situation) this creates.
- Residents at the selected study location alter their normal behavior such as time-activity patterns. Although it is quite certain this will happen to some extent, it is uncertain how much bias (compared to the uncontrolled situation) this creates.
- Either the background levels of exposure, or the absolute levels of exposure (e.g. through diet), are such that the contribution of (in)direct residential exposure cannot be established. The impact will be that it will not be possible to identify hotspots of exposure outside the study locations.

The following go / no go moments have been defined in the project:

- Selection and inclusion of sufficient sites and volunteers from target populations;
- Availability of measurement method(s) for selected pesticides;
- Availability of analytical method(s) for selected pesticides;

8.2 Statutory regulations and required permits

The work is carried out in accordance with a range of statutory regulations, permits etc. Here, relevant regulations and required permits (e.g. concerning medical-ethical evaluation, protection of personal data, use of unusual hazardous chemicals or unusual quantities of chemicals, public private partnerships) are described.

Research in this proposal will be conducted in accordance with applicable guidelines including, the Nuremberg Code of 1947, the revised Declaration of Helsinki in its last version of 2013, the convention for the protection of human rights and dignity of human beings with regard to the application of biology and medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine (Council of Europe, Oviedo, 1997) and its additional protocol concerning biomedical research (Strasbourg, 2005), the recommendation of the committee of ministers to member states in research on biological materials of human origin (Rec (2006)4), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Covenants on Human Rights" (UN General Assembly, December, 1984) and the EU directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

Every partner will comply with all relevant national and EU legislations relating to the conduct of human studies, the study and handling of biological materials and the management of data to protect privacy and maintain confidentiality. Approval of the project plan will be obtained by a medical ethics committee within the framework of the Dutch Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (in Dutch: Wet medisch-wetenschappelijk onderzoek met mensen; WMO). Handling of personal data will comply with the Personal Data Protection Act (in Dutch: Wet bescherming persoonsgegevens; Wbp).

Compliance to ethics regulations will be secured by:

- All investigators in the studies that involve human samples have extensive experience of conducting or participating in research with and the ethical handling and utilization of human material for experimental use.

8.3 Conflicts of interest

Declaration of interest forms of all participating researchers will be collected and updated during the study period.

9 Analysis of choices made and remaining uncertainties

In the design of the study, all potentially relevant environmental exposure routes from professional spraying applications are considered. However, not all scenarios can be studied, hence exposure has to be modelled when extrapolating outside the study area. In the preparation of this study, the project team has revised the OBO-1 protocol and study results, especially with focus on lessons learned.

Uncertainties

Protocols, modeling, and reporting will contain uncertainty numbers and analyses, in accordance (given the nature of each part of the work) with the guidance given in http://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/cms/publicaties/PBL_2013_Guide-for-uncertaintycommunication_1339.pdf

In particular the uncertainties in the modelling (including the collection of data) will be mapped, including a sensitivity analysis. Uncertainties in construct validity need to be addressed first. An important element is the exposure assessment that will be used in the epi-studies. So the construct validity issue here would be something like "How well/poorly do measured/modelled exposure from professionally applied pesticides in orchard describe the actual pesticide exposures in the (general) population."

10 WP2 Organization - Main tasks and responsible entities

UU-IRAS is the lead on WP2. UU-IRAS will focus on the verification of the model framework for sideways and upward spraying, and the translation of the model outputs to personal exposure. Several research institutes play an important role in WP2. The tasks below are discretized per partner.

IRAS

- WP2 project and data management, overall WP2 coordination and study design
- Selection of study area and locations (collaboration with WR-Plant Research and CLM)
- Selection of studied pesticides (collaboration all)
- Collection of biological and environmental samples
- Modeling dispersion and volatilization (collaboration with WR-Plant Research)
- Modeling personal exposure from outdoor air concentrations and indoor dust concentrations of pesticides.
- Statistical analyses of exposure data
- Interpretation of results for measured compounds (collaboration all)

WR-Wageningen Plant Research

- Drift modelling
- Assistance with farmers recruitment (collaboration with CLM)
- Interpretation of results for measured compounds (collaboration all)

WR-Wageningen Food Safety Research

- Analytical methods development
- Targeted chemical analysis of environmental and biomonitoring samples
- Interpretation of results for measured compounds (collaboration all)

CLM Onderzoek en Advies

- Farmers recruitment (collaboration with Marcel Wenneker)
- Fieldwork logistics
- Providing information on pesticides use and application techniques
- Interpretation of results for measured compounds (collaboration all)

RIVM

- External communication and communication across WPs

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